

Evolutionary Analysis of Regulatory Sequences in Promoter of Senescence-induced Glutamine Synthetase cytosolic isozyme *GS1;5* in *Arabidopsis thaliana*

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ABSTRACT:

Glutamine synthetase (GS; EC 6.3.1.2, L-glutamate: ammonia ligase ADP-forming) catalyzes the ATP-dependent addition of ammonium (NH₄⁺) to the γ -carboxyl group of glutamate and produces glutamine. The enzyme is the product of multiple genes with complex promoters that ensure the transcriptional regulation of the genes in an organ- and tissue-specific manner and in response to a number of environmental variables affecting the nutritional status of the plant cell. In the present study we tested for the presence of highly conserved non-coding sequences (CNSs) in the 1000-bp promoter region by analyzing upstream promoter sequences (counted from the translation initiation codon), of *Glutamine Synthetase (GS1;5)* and its orthologous genes. A comparative genome-wide bioinformatic analysis performed for identification of evolutionarily preserved regulatory sequences has revealed highly conserved upstream non-coding sequences (CNSs) within 1000-bp promoter region by analyzing upstream promoter sequences (counted from the translation initiation codon), of *GS1;5* from *Arabidopsis thaliana* and its orthologous genes in various plant species. Two consensus sequences are predicted by sequence logo at the position of -880 bp to -890 bp (CNS1) and -522 bp to -549 bp (CNS2) of *Arabidopsis* promoter region counted from the ATG. Thus identified putative *cis*-regulatory elements in the promoter region of *GS1;5* are expected to allow physical binding of upstream regulatory proteins which are yet to be known, but controlling the senescence-dependent expression of this gene at promoter level in major plant species, under influence of environmental cues to initiate nitrogen remobilization from source to sink.

Keyword: glutamine synthetase, Conserved Regulatory Sequences, Orthologues

INTRODUCTION

Glutamine synthetase (GS) and plant nitrogen metabolism are well known to be continually changed during plant development. Along with GS, a number of other enzymes play key roles in maintaining the balance of carbon and nitrogen during plant development but the central role of GS has been proposed for nitrogen assimilation, flow and remobilization in cereals which are of primary importance to ensure food security due to nitrogen use efficiency, as it is a key target for plant improvement. GS is distributed in different subcellular locations (chloroplast, cytosolic and cytoplasm) and in different tissues and organs depending on the developmental stage of plant. Glutamine synthetases are responsible for the assimilation and re-assimilation of ammonium in young and old leaves, respectively. While the chloroplastic glutamine synthetase GS2 decreases with leaf ageing, while the cytosolic ones (GS1) are induced in the mesophyll of senescing leaves [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. The importance of GS1 isoforms in plant productivity has been shown for maize and rice [6, 7, 8]. Correlation between GS activity and the amount of N remobilized from the shoot to the grain is reported in wheat cultivars [9]. However, the role of the GS1 enzyme is complex because numerous isoforms encoded by a multigenic family exist (three genes in rice, five in maize, and five in *Arabidopsis*). In maize, *GS1-4* is up-regulated during senescence [7]. *Glutamine Synthetase cytosolic isozyme (ATIG48470: GS1;5)* in

Arabidopsis thaliana appears to play a key role in leaf senescence. Previously, the genes coding for the cytosolic glutamine synthetases (HvGS1) barley are identified and the response of the five HvGS1 genes to senescence is studied by using primary and flag leaves. It is strongly noticed that GS genes are not regulated in a similar manner nor they are localized in the same tissues [1]. In *Pinus sylvestris*, two different genes encode GS1, *PsGS1a* and *PsGS1b* [10] having overlapped but distinct expression. *PsGS1a* is expressed almost exclusively in the chlorophyllous parenchyma of photosynthetic tissues, whereas *PsGS1b* is expressed primarily in vascular cells [11]. *PsGS1b* is proposed to play an important role in nitrogen transport. All these reports shows that the molecular mechanisms involved in nitrogen remobilization have been studied for a long time, in several plant species by using both reverse and forward genetics [12], but a systemic approach of comparative *in-silico* analysis among diverse group of species is still lacking. Among species, changes in gene regulation are fundamentally important for [13]. However, gene regulation is poorly understood, especially in plants. Although, it is reported for *PsGS1b* promoter that contains a region rich in previously characterized *cis*-acting elements, known as AC elements and two MYB proteins from loblolly pine (*Pinus taeda*), *PtMYB1* and *PtMYB4*, bind to the *PsGS1b* promoter to activate transcription in yeast, *Arabidopsis* and pine cells (Gómez-

Maldonado et al., 2014), but the underlying molecular mechanisms for transcriptional regulation of *Glutamine synthetase (GS)* in major plant species is yet to be explored for improved understanding knowledge of gene expression that is essential for genomics and evolutionary biology. With the completion of *Arabidopsis* genome sequencing, now there is need to understand gene function, regulation and its variation within and among species. It is well known that functionally important homologous regions in coding sequences tend to be highly conserved between sibling species. Similarly, it is expected that regulatory elements in untranslated regions can be detected by sequence comparison and phylogenetic footprinting [15]. In the present study, we have identified and comprehensively analysed the *GS1;5* gene across the diverse group of species. The work involves the identification of *GS1;5* orthologous gene, a phylogenetic relationship among them and conserved non-coding regulatory motifs in their promoters. By taking the advantage of available expression data in genevestigator for *GS1;5* orthologous gene, we also have performed a comprehensive analysis of tissue specific expression in different plant species, underlying its conserved role upon senescence. Ultimately, these findings will lead to understand *GS1;5* gene regulation and its variation within and among species.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Selection of *GS1;5* gene and expression analysis

In-silico expression profile of the cytosolic isozyme *GS;5* gene was analyzed at developmental and anatomical level by retrieving the expression values from affymetrix array database from Genevestigator response viewer (<https://www.genevestigator.com/gv/>) [16]. For this, microarray expression data were obtained using *Arabidopsis* (ATH1:22 k array), *Oryza sativa* (OS_51 k: Rice Genome 51 k array), *Zea mays* (ZM_84 k: Nimblegen Maize 385 k) and *Glycine max* (GM_60 k: Soybean Genome Array) Gene Chip platform. For each plant species, the identified *GS1;5* gene IDs (see section 2.2) were used as query sequences to perform searches in the Gene Chip platform of Genevestigator, where microarray data from only the wild type background was analyzed.

2.2. Screening for *GS1;5* orthologous genes and retrieval of promoter sequences

Two different approaches were performed to search for *GS1;5* orthologous gene was performed using nucleotide sequence of AT1G48470 (a *GS1;5* from *Arabidopsis thaliana*) as query. In the first approach, the known gene sequence of *GS1;5* from *Arabidopsis* was downloaded from the *Arabidopsis* genome TAIR 9.0 release (<http://www.arabidopsis.org/>) [17], which was used as query sequences to perform multiple database searches against the genome data from the Phytozome (<http://www.phytozome.net/>) [18]. In second approach, the known gene sequence of *GS1;5* from *Arabidopsis* was used to perform BLAST form NCBI (<http://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>) [19]. The accession numbers of *GS1;5* orthologous gene sequences along with the source organism are listed in **Table 1**.

2.3. Sequence alignment and phylogenetic tree construction

38 closest members of *GS1;5* orthologous genes from different species were selected to extract the putative 1000-bp promoter region counted from transcription initiation codon (ATG). The gene annotations and 1-kb promoter regions from various plant species were extracted from NCBI and analyzed the phylogenetic relationship between *GS1;5* orthologous gene. A phylogenetic tree was constructed using MUSCLE multiple sequence alignment tool [20]. The phylogram was visualized through

TreeDyn (<http://www.phylogeny.fr/>) [21]. The *GS1;5* phylogram supported with high bootstrap values, helped in identification of several paralogous (Figure 1, marked in squared brackets) and orthologous genes (Figure 1, marked in curly brackets).

2.4. Searching for conserved non-coding regions in the promoters

A comparative genome-analysis using the 1kb promoter sequences of 13 orthologous genes was performed using the EARS tool (<http://wsbc.warwick.ac.uk/ears/help.php>) [22]. EARS software analyzed each sequence by breaking them into small subsequences (windows) and carried out global alignment between each pair of windows, thus allowed the detection of conserved sequences. For running this analysis, a windows size of 80bp and a cut off *P*-value of 0.008 were used. The EARS result file for each 13 run was also individually analysed by software and the location of the significant peaks was detected within *GS1;5* gene promoter of *Arabidopsis* and its orthologous promoter sequence.

2.5. Over-representative analysis for putative *cis*-elements

To identify putative *cis*-regulatory elements within the Sequences corresponding to the conserved peaks within *GS1;5* promoter sequences derived from the collected candidates of *GS1;5* orthologous genes. In order to examine and extract a set of similar oligonucleotides, representing binding sites for the same upstream TF controlling the expression of *GS1;5* during senescence, two main approaches were used for this task: (1) Extraction of representative set of oligos with a consensus, and (2) Position specific profile characterization of consensus sequences along their alignment in promoter regions. A consensus depicted a set of oligonucleotides with the most frequently occurring nucleotide in each position. This way we could express a set of TFBS with a single oligonucleotide. Over-representative analysis for putative *cis*-elements analysis was done using MEME (<http://meme.sdsc.edu/meme/meme.html>) [23]. The conserved non-coding motifs deduced by MEME were characterized for biological function analysis using protein BLAST, and domains were studied with Interproscan providing the best possible match based on highest similarity score.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Selection and *GS1;5* gene expression analysis among species

In order to identify putative conserved non-coding sequences in promoter of *Glutamine Synthetase cytosolic isozyme (AT1G48470)* in *Arabidopsis thaliana* and its orthologous, combination of *in-silico* approaches are used in a sequential manner, the workflow for which is given in **Figure 1**. First of all, *in-silico* analysis of *GS1;5* gene expression profile was performed using Genevestigator response viewer (<https://www.genevestigator.com/>). The data could be retrieved for *Arabidopsis thaliana* (AT1G48470), *Zea mays* (GRMZM2G036464), *Oryza sativa* (LOC_Os03g50490.1) and *Sorghum bicolor* (Sobic.004G247000)

genes. The data obtained in different developmental stages of plant was retrieved as graphs (**Figure 2**). In developmental stage specific analysis, all four genes exhibited moderate expression throughout life cycle but showing up-regulation in the senescence stage. In case of *Sorghum*, the *GS1;5* gene expression was highly up-regulated at the initial growth phases (from germination to two-leaf stage) followed by moderate expression during the rest of life cycle, and again higher during senescence stage. High expression in the initial as well as finally senescent growth stages in *Sorghum* probably reflects higher requirement

of N-remobilization from source to sink transitions, at these stages of lifecycle. Overall, the analysis indicates that the gene might play some pivotal roles in maintaining well-being transitional stages of the plant during development of life-cycle.

Figure 1. Workflow for de-novo Identification/Prediction of putative cis-regulatory elements in the promoter of GSI;5 .

3.2. Screening for species with GSI;5 gene orthologs via BLAST

For identification of GSI;5 orthologous genes two approaches were used. In the first approach, the known gene sequence of GSI;5 from Arabidopsis, downloaded from the Arabidopsis genome TAIR 9.0 release (<http://www.arabidopsis.org/>), was used as query sequences to perform multiple database searches against the genome data from the Phytozome (<http://www.phytozome.net/>). While, in second approach the known gene sequence of GSI;5 from

Arabidopsis was used as query to perform BLAST from NCBI (<http://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>). The accession numbers of GSI;5 orthologous gene sequences along with the source organism, GeneInfo Identifier for 1000-bp promoter sequences counted from ATG, amino acid identity, length of coding sequences and length of amino acid sequences, are listed in **Table 1**.

Figure 2. Developmental expression patterns of GSI;5 gene in Arabidopsis thaliana, (B) Zea mays, (C) Oryza sativa and (D) Sorghum bicolor.

Table 1. Representing GSI;5 coding orthologous gene accessions and GeneInfo Identifiers for promoter sequences 1-kb in different plant species

GenInfo Identifier	Source organism	Accession	AA Identity	CDs length	AA length
GRMZM2G036464	Zea mays	GRMZM2G036464	71%	930	309
gi 357772479	Vitis vinifera	NP_001268054.1	82%	1071	356
Sobic.004G247000	Sorghum bicolor	Sobic.004G247000	89%	1071	356
gi 953903364	Setaria italic	XP_004953842.1	81%	1071	356
gi 746672156	Sesamum indicum	XP_011085871.1	83%	1071	356
gi 919454360	Pyrus x bretschneideri	NP_001302457.1	82%	1071	356
gi 692196900	Pyrus x bretschneideri	XP_009370058.1	82%	1071	356
gi 692196894	Pyrus x bretschneideri	XP_009370554.1	82%	1071	356
gi 736076222	Populus euphratica	XP_011035558.1	82%	1071	356
LOC_Os03g50490.1	Oryza sativa	LOC_Os03g50490.1	88%	1113	370
gi 651214284	Malus domestica	XP_008365754.1	82%	1071	356
gi 651213880	Malus domestica	XP_008358170.1	82%	1071	356

gi/794732881	<i>Jatropha curcas</i>	XP_012086426.1	83%	1071	356
gi/816020744	<i>Gossypium raimondii</i>	XP_012487952.1	82%	1071	356
gi/952545307	<i>Glycine max</i>	NP_001239821.1	81%	1071	356
gi/460479046	<i>Fragaria vesca subsp. Vesca</i>	XP_004299511.1	82%	1071	356
gi/823681822	<i>Erythranthe guttata</i>	XP_012838271.1	81%	1068	355
gi/823680671	<i>Erythranthe guttata</i>	XP_012845072.1	81%	1071	356
gi/768087738	<i>Cucumis sativus</i>	NP_001267644.1	82%	1071	356
gi/655233050	<i>Cucumis melo</i>	NP_001284433.1	82%	1071	356
gi/725652657	<i>Camelina sativa</i>	XP_010500377.1	94%	1065	354
gi/725652659	<i>Camelina sativa</i>	XP_010505938.1	84%	1065	354
gi/725652645	<i>Camelina sativa</i>	XP_010465841.1	84%	1065	354
gi/679811890	<i>Brassica rapa</i>	XP_009147968.1	96%	1074	357
gi/679811898	<i>Brassica rapa</i>	XP_009145973.1	83%	1065	354
gi/919506257	<i>Brassica oleracea</i>	XP_013590383.1	96%	1074	357
gi/919506440	<i>Brassica oleracea</i>	XP_013622724.1	83%	1065	354
gi/919506526	<i>Brassica oleracea</i>	XP_013636878.1	82%	1065	354
gi/919506383	<i>Brassica oleracea</i>	XP_013637496.1	81%	1071	356
gi/919454273	<i>Brassica napus</i>	NP_001302737.1	84%	1065	354
gi/919454360	<i>Brassica napus</i>	NP_001302957.1	83%	1065	354
gi/919454177	<i>Brassica napus</i>	XP_013655508.1	83%	1065	354
gi/919454360	<i>Brassica napus</i>	XP_013725462.1	82%	1065	354
gi/919454419	<i>Brassica napus</i>	XP_013642389.1	82%	1065	354
gi/919453855	<i>Brassica napus</i>	XP_013706743.1	81%	1071	356
gi/240254421	<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	AT1G48470	100%	1062	353
gi/240255695	<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	NP_188409.1	83%	1065	354

3.3. Sequences alignment and phylogenetic tree construction

Although, the structural and functional importance of divergent *GS1;5* gene evolution still remains unclear, however the promoter sequences of the *GS1;5* orthologous genes were expected to show close association among various plant species in order to conserve the biological role of the gene and at least its expression. Phylogenetic analysis and phylogram supported with high bootstrap values, helped in prediction of consensus promoter sequence among and within species indicating conservatively in their sequences. A phylogenetic tree thus constructed with high confidence using neighbor-joining method (Figure 3), exemplifies their ancestral relationships. Tree is built aligned each sequence using *GS1;5* 1-kb promoter from *Arabidopsis thaliana* as query and thirty most similar sequences determined by BLAST.

3.4. Searching for conserved non-coding regions in the *GS1;5* promoter

As promoter regions are functionally important for gene expression and are expected to be conserved during evolution, we applied a newly developed comparative genomics technique (2) to identify regulatory modules that are conserved between *GS1;5* orthologs from distant species. Figure 4 shows that the region comprising the conserved motifs exhibits a significant level of conservation between *Arabidopsis* and distant species enlisted in Table 2, including *Oryza sativa*, *Zea mays*, *Vitis vinifera* and several others. The region of significant conservation is classified into two, consensus 1 (indicated with

curly RED colored bracket) and consensus 2 (indicated with curly black colored bracket). Both consensus regions may possess conserved motifs functionally important for gene expression as novel *cis*-regulatory elements. This finding has potential to be proved by experimental approaches.

Figure 3. Maximum likelihood bootstrap consensus phylogeny of 1- kb sequence of the *GS1,5* promoter. Neighbor-joining

distance tree based with bootstrap support is given along the branches.

Figure 4. Identification of Evolutionarily Conserved Sequences within the Promoter of GS1;5. (A) GS1;5 individual conservation profile between the Arabidopsis GS1;5 promoter and each orthologous promoters given in Table 2. 1000 bases upstream of the translational start site of the GS1;5 gene were aligned using the EARS tool with a 80-base window length. The dotted red line indicates the significance threshold of P = 0.008. Peaks above this threshold indicate that the window has a highly conserved match in the other species. (A) Consensus sequence 1 (CNS1) is highlighted with RED curly bracket. (B) Consensus sequence 2 (CNS2) is highlighted with BLACK curly bracket at the location of conservativity. Due to their low complexity, consensus 1 and 2 has given a high conservation score.

Table 2. Selected orthologous gene used for identification of evolutionarily conserved sequences within the Promoter of GS1;5

Accession	GenInfo Identifier	Source
GRMZM2G036464	GRMZM2G036464	Zea mays
NP_001268054.1	gi 357772479	Vitis vinifera
XP_004953842.1	gi 953903364	Setaria italic
XP_011085871.1	gi 746672156	Sesamum indicum
XP_011035558.1	gi 736076222	Populus euphratica
LOC_Os03g50490.1	LOC_Os03g50490.1	Oryza sativa
XP_008365754.1	gi 651214284	Malus domestica
NP_001267644.1	gi 768087738	Cucumis sativus
NP_001284433.1	gi 655233050	Cucumis melo
XP_010465841.1	gi 725652645	Camelina sativa
XP_013655508.1	gi 919454177	Brassica napus
AT1G48470	gi 240254421	Arabidopsis thaliana

3.5. Over-representative analysis for putative cis-elements in conserved non-coding regions

As we found two peaks above the threshold significance threshold of P = 0.008 which indicates that the window has a highly conserved match in the other species. Therefore to identify the identified motif sequence at this region of

promoters, MEME suit was used which revealed two consensus sequences between positions of -500 to -1000 of promoter (Figure 5). CNS1 revealed a conserved motif in *GS1;5* promoter form *Arabidopsis thaliana* between positions -522 and -549. The consensus sequence 1 reflected the oligosequence of CG(A/T)A(C/G)C N N N N N N N N [GGG] N N N N C N N N C A C consisted of a GGG core sequence. CNS2 also revealed a short conserved motif in *GS1;5* promoter form *Arabidopsis thaliana* between positions -880 and -898, with oligosequence of TGGCTA(T/G) N N N N N N N N G. The positional profiles of these motifs in orthologous species are shown in Figure 5. These putative cis-regulatory elements within the promoter of *GLN1;5* with a set of similar oligonucleotides may represent the binding sites for the same upstream TF controlling the expression of *GLN1;5* upon senescence. These results indicate that the promoter region between -500 and -1000 bp, harboring CNS1 and CNS2 is required for senescence-specific expression of *GS1;5*.

Figure 5. Cumulative conservation profile between the Arabidopsis GS1;5 promoter and orthologous promoters from distant species. (A) 1000 bases upstream of the translational start site of the GS1;5 gene were aligned using the EARS tool for identifying the evolutionary conserved regulator regions. (B) Showing positional profile and consensus sequence 1 with Logo

within GS1;5 promoter from various plant species. (C) Showing positional profile and consensus sequence 2 with Logo within GS1;5 promoter from various plant species.

4. CONCLUSION

Our evolutionary analysis of regulatory sequences by phylogenetic approach has revealed two highly conserved consensus regions with position specific motifs within -500 to -1000 bp, *GS1;5* promoter of *Arabidopsis thaliana* and its orthologous distant species. Currently, almost nothing is known about molecular mechanism of *GS1;5* expression and up-stream regulatory proteins. However, in future one might consider to employ the yeast-one hybrid system to screen for upstream transcription factors binding to the *GS1;5* promoter, driving senescence activity.

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